

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Fractional Domination Number of the Fractal Graphs

G Uma¹, S Amutha^{2*}, N Anbazhagan¹, P Shanthi¹

¹ Department of Mathematics, Alagappa University, Karaikudi, Karaikudi, 630 003, Tamil Nadu

² Ramanujan Centre for Higher Mathematics, Alagappa University, Karaikudi, 630 003, Tamil Nadu, India

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* **Corresponding author.**

amuthas@alagappauniversity.ac.in

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Abstract

Background/Objectives: A fractal is a collection of clearly defined structures that are uneven or irregular and can be divided into smaller pieces. Each of these smaller pieces has a relationship to the overall structure at random ranges that are analogous or identical. Fractal graphs are a highly effective way to construct well-defined patterns. The fractional domination number in a graph refers to the weight of a minimum fractional dominating function. The study is to find the bounds of the fractional domination and their related parameters in the fractal graphs. **Methods:** The sharp bounds and the constant ratio of fractional domination and their related parameters were calculated using an iterative process in all iterations of a self-similarity fractal graph. **Findings:** The study established the relation between the fractional domination number and other relevant parameters as fractional independence domination numbers for each iteration in the fractal graphs and explained how the concept of fractional domination works on fractal graphs such as the Koch snowflake and the Sierpinski triangle. **Novelty:** Previous researchers have studied bounds on maximum matching and dominating sets in fractal graphs such as the Koch snowflake and the Sierpinski triangle. The present study enhances the idea of finding the bounds of fractional domination parameters in a fractal graph. The construction of new beautiful ornaments, locating damaged cells for drug injection in medical science, placing stones in jewels, plumping work, and designing fractal antennas all can be made possible by this work in self-similarity fractal graphs.

Keywords: Fractals; Fractional Dominating Functions; Fractional Domination Number; Fractional Independence Domination Number; Fractional Domination Chain

1 Introduction

Let G be a fractal graph with vertices and edges. The special characteristics of graphs, such as self-similarity, recursive function, and detailed structure at arbitrary tiny scales, are present in fractal graphs. Fractals are beautiful visuals that have people in awe. Fractals are regarded as things with well-defined self-similarity. Each of these items,

regardless of how they were split or divided, retains the same characteristics and a mathematically determined structure. The Koch snowflake is one of the better-known early fractals. Koch Island or Koch Star are other names for Koch snowflake. It has been developed iteratively at various phases. Each subsequent step is created by adding outward folds to every side of the initial, equilateral triangle, resulting in a smaller triangle. In each repetition, the curve's overall length increased by $\frac{4}{3}$. The line segment from the previous iteration is multiplied by four in each subsequent iteration. The Koch snowflake has 3×4^m vertices in its m^{th} iteration. In classical geometry, the Sierpinski triangle is the most well-known fractal graph. Inside, it is made entirely of triangles. It consists of an overall equilateral triangle with equal lengths on each of its three sides. The inside of the structure is entirely composed of triangles. It is applied in building construction and jewelry design. An equilateral triangle can be used as a starting point for a Sierpinski triangle. Attach the center of the triangle to each side, forming another equilateral triangle. This process can be repeated to cover $\frac{3}{4}$ of the original triangle. The remaining portion can be removed. Each side of the triangle is reduced by $\frac{1}{3}$ of its initial length. Continuously follow these steps to create new structures at each iteration. The Sierpinski triangle has an infinite area and diameter. It consists of 3^s edges in each iteration. A function $f: V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a "Fractional Dominating Functions" if, for each vertex v in the vertex set $V, \sum_{u \in N[v]} f(u) \geq 1$. The minimum weight of all other fractional dominating functions is called fractional domination number denoted by $\gamma_f(G)$ ⁽¹⁾. An independent function $f: V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a maximal independent function (MIF) if for every $v \in V$ with $f(v)=0$, we have $\sum_{u \in N[v]} f(u) \geq 1$. The fractional independent domination numbers are denoted as $i_f(G)$, which is defined as the minimum cardinality of the set $\{f\}$: f is an MIF of G ⁽²⁾. In ⁽³⁾, which is based on fractal geometry and deduces some of the properties of fractal graphs, ⁽⁴⁾ investigated the effects of deviations composing the fractal of the Sierpinski triangle, and ⁽⁵⁾ presented the design and simulation of a Koch curve fractal antenna. In ⁽⁶⁾, complex networks use combinatorial methods and algorithms for studying fractal properties. The results of the effectiveness confirmation and feasibility studies of using a fractal algorithm for making stronger structures are covered in ⁽⁷⁾. Some bounds and effects of removing a vertex on the fractional domination number are discussed in ⁽⁸⁾. In ⁽⁹⁾, the results of bounds or the exact value of the total domination number of new graphs are obtained. Extend the result to the range on incidence graphs using the fractional total domatic numbers given in ⁽¹⁰⁾. ⁽¹¹⁾ proposed the idea of finding the dominating sets in the linear benzenoid graph as fractals. The maximal matching and dominating sets on fractal graphs were found in recent studies ^(12,13). We assessed the bounds of fractional domination number and related parameters in the fractal graph, motivated by the development of the fractional concept.

2 Methodology

Fractional domination number of a Koch snowflake

Let K_m be the Koch snowflake consisting of 3×4^m vertices and edges, where m is the iteration. i.e., each iteration of the Koch Snowflake appears to have a self-similarity fractal structure, as shown in Figure 1 ⁽¹²⁾.

Fig 1. Koch Snowflake

Theorem 2.1

The Koch snowflake consists of 3×4^m vertices and edges of each iteration. Then, it has the common ratio between the number of vertices and the cardinality number of the fractional domination number. i.e., for every iteration, the fractional domination number of the Koch snowflake, $\gamma_f(K_m) = \frac{3 \times 4^m}{3}$ where $m \geq 0$.

Proof

Let K_m be the Koch snowflake, which consists of 3×4^m vertices in each iteration. When $m = 0$, the initial iteration of Koch snowflake is an equilateral triangle. The value of the vertices is assigned by the definition of the fractional domination number, as shown in Figure 2.

Either way, the fractional domination number is the same for adding the weight of minimum dominating functions. i.e, $\gamma_f(K_0) = 1 + 0 + 0 = \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3} = 1$. When $m = 1$, the first iteration of a Koch snowflake has $3 \times 4^1 = 12$ vertices, and the fractional domination number $\gamma_f(K_1) = \frac{3 \times 4^1}{3} = 4$ is calculated as shown in Figure 3.

Hence, either way for the first iteration,

3 Results and Discussion

Fractional Domination Number of a Sierpinski Triangle

Let T_s be the Sierpinski triangle consisting of 3^s edges where $s \geq 1$ is the iteration. i.e., each iteration of the Sierpinski triangle appears to have a self-similarity fractal structure, as shown in Figure 5⁽¹²⁾.

Fig 5. Sierpinski Triangle

Theorem 3.1

The Sierpinski triangle has 3^s edges where $s \geq 1$ is the iteration. Then, in the first iteration, the Sierpinski triangle of 3 edges has 1 fractional domination number; in the second iteration, 9 edges have $\frac{3}{2}$ of fractional domination number; and the next level of iterations has 3^{s-2} where ($s \geq 3$) of fractional domination number.

$$\text{i. e. } \gamma_f(T_s) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1 \quad s = 1 \\ \frac{3}{2} \quad s = 2 \\ 3^{s-2} \quad s \geq 3 \end{array} \right\}$$

Proof

The Sierpinski triangle has 3^s edges where s is the iteration. When $s = 1$ in the first iteration of the Sierpinski triangle is an equilateral triangle and it has 3 edges and 1 of fractional domination number is shown in Figure 6.

Fig 6. T_1

Hence, in both ways, $\gamma_f(T_1) = \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3} = 1 + 0 + 0 = 1$. When $s = 2$, Sierpinski triangle has $3^2 = 9$ edges and the $\frac{3}{2}$ of fractional domination number is shown in Figure 7.

Fig 7. T_2

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Declaration

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